

1. General Company and Interviewee Information

Meta-Information about Companies and Partners (5 min)

- May we record the interview for a transcript?
- Domain of the Company:
 - Which **sector** does the company belong to? (e.g. finance, healthcare, retail, technology, etc.)
 - How should the **company size** be classified? (SME, large company, etc.)
- Information to interviewee:
 - Could you please describe your **professional career**, explain your background and briefly describe your current role in the company?
 - How many years of **professional experience** do you already have?
 - Could you please describe your expertise in large language models and the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) concept?

2. Status of RAGs in the company

RQ1: How has the industry adapted to the rapidly evolving landscape of large language models (LLMs) and their specific domain-specific knowledge?

- When and how did your company start to deal with LLMs? Which employees were involved and how?

3. Insights and Future of RAGs

RQ2: How have companies applied RAG in their use cases, and can specific implementation patterns be identified?

RQ3: What **opportunities** do companies see when implementing and using LLMs (RAG systems) – technically and organizationally?

RQ4: What **challenges** do companies face when implementing and using LLMs (RAG systems) – technically and organizationally?

- Has a RAG approach, i.e. the combination of LLM with knowledge enrichment, already been used in your company, or is it currently being planned?
 - Which **application(s)** is a RAG currently used in your company? For which target group is the LLM (RAG) used?
 - What is the **objective/advantage** of using a RAG for you?
- Can you give us an insight into your **technological infrastructure** for implementing the RAG?
- How would you currently assess the **technological readiness level** (TRL) of the RAGs application? Answer with a number between 1 and 9 (1-3 Research, 4-6 Development, 7-9 Deployment)
- Are there any specific **challenges** or **lessons learned** in implementing RAG that you can / would like to mention?

4. Quality criteria for the RAG

RQ5: What quality implications do companies set for RAG systems, and how are these standards implemented in practice?

a) Quality criteria

- Let's assume you want to use your RAG for a specific target group. What specific **quality requirements** do you have for the productive use of RAG? List these step by step and explain why.
- Rate/Sort the following requirements? Explain why for each.
 - RAG/Answer Quality
 - Explainability and Transparency
 - Integration in Setup
 - Chat-Interface / Usability
 - Security
 - Privacy / Data protection
 - Ethical/biases
 - Continuous Learning/Operation
 - Costs
 - Scalability
 - Licensing/copyright
 - Performance

b) Metrics (Measurability)

- Do you access specific **metrics** to measure your RAG quality? If yes, which metrics are used to assess the quality of the RAG? (e.g. NPS, user satisfaction, acceptance rate)

4. Concluding questions and outlook

- Which of the **goals** were implemented/achieved, and which were not?
- What **potential**, but also risks, do you see in using RAG for your company?
- Do you have any other contacts within the company or with other companies?
- Do you want to be anonymized?